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The Formation of Shanghai School of Calligraphy

Hu Chuanhai

Abstract

Shanghai possesses all the essential conditions for forming an art school: a favorable geographical environment, a relaxed political atmosphere, strong economic momentum, outstanding artistic leaders, a vast group of collectors, numerous art organizations, powerful publishing media, and an excellent educational heritage. All these factors contributed to the birth of the Shanghai School of Calligraphy. This school has become one of the most vibrant art movements in modern and contemporary Chinese art, continuing to exert its influence.

Key Words

Cultural diversity, interest-driven, core strength, psychological identification

The Xinhai Revolution overthrew the Qing Dynasty, causing many nobles to lose their privileged positions and power. Consequently, they moved away from Beijing, a city that had become a source of bitterness for them, to cities with a more relaxed political atmosphere and better economic conditions. Among these cities, Shanghai was the most favored, followed by Qingdao, Tianjin, Guangzhou, Xuzhou, Nanjing, Nanchang, and Suzhou. According to Liu Chengyu's *Memories of the World-Taking Hall* (Shizai House), "Hu Xiaoshi stated, After the Xinhai Revolution, the former ministers of the Qing court settled in two main places: one was Qingdao, where they relied on the protection of the Germans. Many princes and high-ranking officials, such as Prince Gong and Prince Su, lived there to facilitate their escape to Japan, Korea, or Manchuria; the other was Shanghai, where the highest-ranking former Grand Councilor, Qu Hongji, resided along with Shen Zipei (Zengzhi) and Li Mei'an (Ruiqing) as the core members. Xiaoshi lived in Mei'an's home, gaining insights into the actions of the former ministers in both Qingdao and Shanghai." At that time, the former officials and social elites who had a significant influence and were residing in Shanghai included Chen Baochen, Shen Zengzhi, Chen Sanli, Li Ruiqing, Qu Hongji, Chen Kuilong, Feng Xu, Zhu Zumou, Kang Youwei, Zeng Xi, Zhang Jian, Yuan Shuxun,

Liu Chenggan, Fan Zengxiang, and Zhang Yuanji. In contrast, those residing in Qingdao included Yu Shimei, Liu Tingchen, Zhao Erxun, Zhou Fu, Lu Runxiang, Lao Naixuan, and Gu Hongming. In terms of both the number of people and their social status and influence, Shanghai had a clear advantage.¹ Moreover, most of the residents in Shanghai were part of the "Emperor Party", while those in Qingdao belonged to the "Empress Party", and their political ideologies were incompatible. The group of former officials residing in Shanghai constituted the core strength of the Haipai art movement. They laid the foundation for the aesthetic preferences and values in calligraphy and painting of that era.

Haipai paintings and calligraphy are considered the most important art movements of the modern era primarily because of this "core strength". The formation of an art movement depends on whether the location has favorable political, economic, cultural, artistic, and geographical conditions. Politically, the atmosphere at Shanghai School was much more relaxed than that of the Beijing School. Shanghai's status as the largest financial center in the Far East supported and led to significant commercial prosperity. The coexistence of Chinese and Western cultures, the opening of the five treaty ports, and the influx of talent from various regions, all seeking profit, gave Shanghai hope and vitality. Zhang Mingke

mentioned in the sixth volume of *The Anecdotes of the Cold Pine Pavilion*: “At that time, Shanghai, ever since the opening of the sea ban, has flourishing trade like no other place. Those who lived off their art also flocked to Shanghai, selling their paintings, with (Hu) Gongshou and (Ren) Bonian being the most outstanding.” This led to the formation of a group of Haipai painters and calligraphers represented by Zhang Zixiang, Ren Xiong, Ren Xun, Hu Gongshou, Xu Gu, Ren Bonian, Pu Hua, Qian Huian, and Wu Changshuo, among whom Ren Bonian, Xu Gu, Pu Hua, and Wu Changshuo stood out as the “Four Masters of Haipai”. This artistic force appeared as pure artists and created a group effect. They were true “professional painters and calligraphers” who presented themselves as a collective. They lived in various social strata and brought a sense of psychological identity to society, embodying the image of “Haipai painters and calligraphers”.²

However, the formation of the Haipai painting and calligraphy group inevitably involved some key figures or small groups. These individuals had keen political awareness, cultural sentiment, considerable influence, and exceptional artistic vision. At that time, Shen Zengzhi was one of them, playing a central role. The saying “Seeking friends with a harmonious voice” reflects a person’s social activities and indicates their social position and the extent of their influence within their circle of friends. Let’s look at the people in Shen Zengzhi’s “circle of friends”: Zeng Nongran, Pan Zuyin, Wu Changshuo, Li Ruiqing, Chen Sanli, Wang Guowei, Yu Zhaokang, Luo Shuyan, Zhang Yuanji, Zheng Xiaoxu, Zhang Yishan, Ma Yifu, Zhu Zhengzhuang, Hu Puan, Kang Youwei, among others. These were high-ranking officials from the former dynasty, leaders in the art world, and academic giants of their time. Shen Zengzhi became a “manager” or “night watchman” in this cultural circle. Kang Youwei was a prominent figure, but his political experience was less extensive than Shen Zengzhi’s. During a critical moment, Shen advised Kang to be patient. Kang later said: “In the 14th year of Guangxu, I fervently submitted a lengthy memorial urging timely reform... Officials attacked it. Shen Zipei (Shen Zengzhi) advised not to speak of state affairs and to focus on calligraphy and epigraphy instead. At that time, I resided in the ‘Hanman Boat’, where old trees overshadowed the sky, and I dedicated my days to reading stele (rubblings), having viewed several thousand types of epigraphic collections from the capital. (The rubblings made) before the 13th year of Guangxu’s reign was almost viewed by me. I intended to write a book on epigraphy, following in the footsteps of Bao Shenbo’s *Extensive Art and Crafting Double Oars*.”³ Of course, most of the conversations between Shen Zengzhi and his

friends were related to calligraphy and art. For example, his exchanges with Zheng Xiaoxu, a significant figure in modern Chinese history, on calligraphy were meaningful. Zheng Xiaoxu noted in his diary: “On March 2, 1900, I took three leaves of *the Thousand Character Classic* by *Huaisu* from Zipei’s place. Upon careful inspection, I noticed something new, understanding that the ancients must have held their wrists high to maneuver the brush extraordinarily.”⁴ On September 24, the third year of the Republic of China, Zheng noted, “In the morning, I visited Zipei and met Yu Huiruo. We talked for a long time. I showed Zipei the cursive characters I had recently written. Zipei said, ‘Xue Daozu tried to achieve this style but failed, and Emperor Gaozong of Song had similar intentions but could not do it well either. You should know that this path is not easily found.’ I replied, ‘You once praised the grandeur and freedom of clerical cursive, but I dislike the vulgarity of cursive script’s uninhibited strokes, so I aim to follow the style of Huang Xiang and Suo Jing.’”⁵ Shen Zengzhi’s interactions with Wu Changshuo allowed him to reassess Wu’s paintings. In September 1913, Shen titled his residence “Hai Ri Lou” and drew a painting. He later asked Wu Changshuo to paint the building. Initially, Shen was displeased with Wu’s sketchy style, but after closely examining it, he realized each stroke was like an ancient seal script, full of vitality. He apologized to Wu. Shen later recorded this event in his 1920 *Lu Ji*: “One day, I asked Mr. Fou (i.e., Wu) to paint my building. The resulting sketch did not seem like a painting, but after mounting it, it exuded vitality. I told Mr. Fou: ‘You have portrayed my building and my poetry.’” Shen’s suggestion to Li Ruiqing to incorporate the stele script into the running script was also significant. Li later remarked: “I never understood ‘The Preface of Orchid Pavilion,’ and Mr Shen Yian often scolded me for it.”⁶ Li eventually turned to the Northern Wei stele style, greatly influenced by Shen. Li said: “In recent years, during the turmoil in Shanghai, I made a living by selling calligraphy. Shen Zipei urged me to incorporate stele scripts into my running script...Therefore, I studied various calligraphic models during the intense summer heat, choosing from the *Chunhua Ge Tie*, *Daguan Tie*, and *Jiangzhou Tie*. If I could not grasp the methods of their brushwork, I would write them in the stele script style.”⁷ Although Shen Zengzhi and Zeng Xi did not interact frequently, their discussions on calligraphy were fascinating. “Zeng Nongran (i.e., Zeng Xi) once said: ‘I evaluate Meisou’s (i.e., Shen) calligraphy and (I think) its strength lies in its clumsiness, its wonder in its rawness, and its superiority in its instability... Nongran said: ‘Weng Qinxi (i.e., Weng Fanggang) misspent his life because of stability. Shian

(i.e., Liu Yong) reached instability in his eighties, and Yuansou (i.e., He Shaoji) became even more unstable after seventy, constantly taking risks. The more instability (he pursued), the more wonder (shown in his calligraphy).’ Meisou humbly replied: ‘I cannot achieve that, but I will strive with my old wrist, not knowing if I can reach that instability.’”⁸ Such exchanges between masters significantly promoted the advancement of both parties’ calligraphy. The people who interacted with Shen Zengzhi were the top figures in the art world at the time. Their aesthetic views greatly influenced various social strata.

Due to the influx of people from other regions seeking livelihoods in Shanghai, various artistic schools gradually emerged. Contemporary calligraphers who followed Shen Meisou included Ma Yifu, Wang Quchang, Xie Wuliang, Zou Mengchan, and Xie Fengsun. Those who followed Kang Youwei included Xiao Xian, Liu Xiang, and Li Peiji. Followers of Li Ruiqing included Li Zhongqian, Liu Haisu, and Liu Jieyu. Those who followed Zeng Nongran included Zhang Daqian, Jiang Guobang, and Ma Qizhou. Followers of Wu Changshuo included Wang Geyi, Zhao Yunhuo, Fei Longding, Wang Yingbin, Zhao Yucun, and Wu Dongmai. Followers of Zheng Taiyi included Cao Rangheng, Zhao Zunyue, and Zeng Xueli. Followers of Tan Chaling included Tan Shu and Yue Sen. Followers of Zhang Jizhi included Hua Jie’an. Followers of Yu Qu Yuan included Sanliu Qiao. Followers of Yu

Youren included Zhou Bomin. Followers of Hu Hanmin included Li Xianguan, Ren Zhongmin, Huang Naichang, and Pan Qinmeng. Followers of Deng Chengxiu included Deng Mengxiang and Deng Zhongguo. Followers of Liang Dingfen included Yang Ziyuan. Followers of Shen Jianchao included Shen Yuhuan. Followers of Qian Mingshan included Qian Xiaoshan. Followers of Yuan Kewen included Cao Jingtao, Zheng Zibao, Chao Zhangfu, Wang Datie, and Yu Yifen. There were many followers of Zhao Zhiqian, including Yi Daan, Ma Gongyu, Li Mingke, Qin Bowei, Zhao Junmin, and Fu Shouyi.⁹ Top figures led and influenced various aesthetic fields, creating the diverse and colorful characteristics of the Haipai style. As Cheng Shifa once said, “Haipai has no faction,” meaning that Haipai cannot be summarized or characterized by a single model. In reality, these artistic streams were unified under the banner of Haipai. The greatest characteristic of Haipai art is its inclusiveness. This inclusiveness means that various artistic propositions and practices could find space to develop in Shanghai, allowing for independent development without interference from one another. This is why Haipai art presents a colorful and vibrant scene. As a result, a “siphon effect” occurred in the Shanghai art world, attracting painters from nearby cities and counties to Shanghai (the earliest artistic form of Haipai is painting). Consequently, a group of professional painters and calligraphers began to form. Below, I will use Mr.

1	Zhao Zhiqian	Shaoxing	1829-1884	Skilled in seal carving and calligraphy, adept at painting flowers and vegetables, with numerous publications.
2	Xugu	She Xian	1823-1896	Expert in painting flowers, fruits, birds, fish, and landscapes, and skilled in poetry.
3	Ren Yi	Shaoxing	1840-1896	Skilled in painting figures, flowers, feathers, landscapes, and especially portraits, as well as in calligraphy and poetry
4	Wu Changshuo	Anji	1844-1927	Skilled in calligraphy and painting, seal carving, and especially adept in the art of the Stone Drum inscriptions.
5	Huang Binhong	She Xian	1864-1955	Skilled in landscape painting, proficient in poetry, and adept in calligraphy and seal carving.
6	Ren Xiong	Xiaoshan	1823-1857	Skilled in painting figures, land-scapes, flowers and birds, insects and fish, and animals, with particular expertise in deities and Buddhist and Taoist figures.
7	Pu Hua	Jiaxing	1834-1911	Skilled in poetry, proficient in calligraphy and painting, with particular expertise in landscapes, flowers, and ink bamboo.
8	Hu Gongshou	Shanghai	1823-1886	Proficient in landscapes, orchids, bamboo, flowers, calligraphy, and poetry

9	Zhang Xiong	Jiaxing	1803-1886	Skilled in flower painting, feathered subjects, and proficient in figure painting, landscapes, and seal carving.
10	Wu Youru	Suzhou	?-1893	Specializes in portraiture, primarily known for illustrating the “Dian Shizhai Pictorial” in Shanghai.
11	Chen Zhang	Xinan	1869-1938	Specializes in meticulous flower painting, especially skilled in life drawing with vivid colors and lifelike imagery
12	Wu Qingyun	Nanjing	?-1916	Specializes in landscape painting, particularly adept at capturing misty and rainy scenes, and incorporates techniques from Western watercolor painting
13	Ren Xun	Xiaoshan	1835-1893	Specializes in figure and landscape painting, with particular expertise in painting flowers and birds
14	Qian Huian	Shanghai	1833-1911	Skilled in painting figures, ladies, flowers, and landscapes.
15	Sha Fu	Suzhou	1830-1906	Skilled in painting figures, ladies, and flowers, also proficient in seal carving.
16	Huang Shanshou	Changzhou	1855-1919	Skilled in painting figures, landscapes, flowers, ink dragons, and calligraphy.
17	Ni Mogeng	Jiangdu	1855-1919	Skilled in painting figures, ladies, and Buddha images, especially at depicting birds and animals, and proficient in landscapes.
18	Zhao Ziyun	Suzhou	1873-1955	Skilled in painting flowers and landscapes, also proficient in seal carving and cursive script.
19	Wang Yiting	Wuxing	1867-1938	Proficient in calligraphy and painting, skilled in landscapes, flowers and birds, figures, and animals, especially adept at depicting Buddhist images.
20	Feng Chaoran	Changzhou	1882-1954	Skilled in landscapes and flowers, excels in painting women; proficient in calligraphy, including cursive, seal, and clerical scripts, and also adept at seal carving.
21	Zheng Wuchang	Shengxian	1894-1952	Skilled in landscape painting, with additional expertise in flowers and fruits, ink bamboo, vegetables, and calligraphy.

Ding Huizeng’s chart¹⁰ to illustrate this.

The influx of numerous calligraphers and painters to Shanghai was largely driven by economic interests, which also laid the foundation for the professional calligrapher and painter community. Shanghai’s art market had strong purchasing power. Therefore, besides the relaxed political atmosphere, the city’s substantial economic strength was the second key factor in forming this art movement. Ge Yuanxu mentioned in *Notes on Touring Shanghai*: “Shanghai is an area for merchants, and eccentric literati and artists often gather here.” As the economy improved, there was an increasing demand for collecting calligraphy and paintings as gifts or appreciation. This group included wealthy merchants,

prominent families, well-known artists, foreigners, and expatriates. “Among them were consuls, agents, foreign merchants, bank directors, managers, engineers, and journalists, mainly British, followed by many Japanese who came to Shanghai to set up businesses, trade, and practice medicine. They also became major collectors of Shanghai School art. Some Japanese art dealers even organized exhibitions for Shanghai School artists in Japan, such as at the Kyubundo, Shikido, Nagasaki Shoshuen, and Osaka Takashimaya galleries, which hosted exhibitions of works by Wu Changshuo and Wang Yiting, among others.”¹¹ Some industrialists, possessing financial resources and artistic vision, supported the art community with their substantial capital, making large

purchases of high-value and high-quality pieces. Wang Qisen described in *Essays on Shanghai School Art*: “Figures like Pang Yuanji and Zhang Congyu represented such collectors. Pang Yuanji was a prominent collector, and Wang Jiqian described him as ‘the largest collector of Chinese calligraphy and painting in the world, possessing thousands of renowned works.’ The Pang family from Huzhou, Zhejiang, was renowned for their silk industry as early as the Ming Dynasty. Pang Yuanji had a room for storing paintings in his residence on Chengdu North Road in Shanghai, named ‘Xuzhai’. He employed well-known Shanghai School artists like Lu Hui and Zhang Dazhuang to authenticate and catalog his collection. Lu Hui had been a staff member of Wu Daheng and a consultant for Sheng Xuanhuai in identifying calligraphy and paintings. He worked at Pang’s ‘Xuzhai’ for twenty years, and Zhang also worked there for ten years, reflecting the vastness of Pang’s collection. They compiled the classic catalogues *Xuzhai Collection of Paintings* in 20 volumes and *Supplementary Catalogue* in 4 volumes.” Another example is Zhou Xiangyun, a major real estate dealer in Shanghai, who collected hundreds of bronze artifacts from three generations, including two prestigious pieces of Qi State bronze. He also collected many famous inscriptions and calligraphy pieces from various dynasties, such as Yu Shinan’s *Inscription of Princess Ru Nan* and Huaisu’s *Bitter Bamboo*. Additionally, figures like Hu Gongshou and Wang Yiting had significant business achievements and strength.¹²

These collectors invested in ancient treasures and collected contemporary calligraphy and paintings from renowned artists. Of course, a significant part of the purchasing power came from the middle class. Although they had the financial means, their appreciation skills were often inferior to those of the elite. Sometimes, their collecting habits seemed superficial. Such a vast art market made artists more pragmatic and rational. Wu Changshuo, discussing the relationship between art and life, said: “The pursuit of elegance and fashion is often criticized, but in reality, elegance cannot be devoid of followers, otherwise, it would be in danger of starving to death.”¹³ Wu Changshuo was initially unfamiliar with landscape painting. He did not want to miss the opportunity when someone was willing to pay for such works. He would commission landscape artists to create drafts, which he then copied. In short, he was determined not to let this money slip away. He also noted that many people judged arts based on the fame of the artists rather than true artistic understanding: “One day, while chatting with a friend, my friend said that most of the world’s appraisers used their ears rather than their eyes. I replied, if they were good at using their eyes, we would starve.”¹⁴

Wu Changshuo was also lenient towards the counterfeit paintings of his works. A man who purportedly wanted to buy a painting of plum blossoms from Wu Changshuo asked Wu to verify its authenticity. Wu, after examining it, declared it genuine. At that time, Huifeng was present and remarked, “How could his painting be genuine when your name in the inscription is An Xing (安杏) and not An Ji (安吉, which is Wu’s hometown).” Wu Changshuo smiled and said, “I am old, and errors in writing are inevitable.” Later, when the buyer took the painting, Wu told Huifeng, “Although I know it is not my work, I choose not to expose it. By doing this, art dealers can make a living, which benefits them and does not harm me. Why should I be so serious?”¹⁵ This shows that Wu Changshuo had a sophisticated social experience. It also indicated that calligraphers and painters had their survival strategies in a commercially-driven society.

The third important factor in the formation of the Shanghai School was the establishment of artist societies for mutual support. During the late Qing Dynasty and early Republic of China, Shanghai’s calligraphers and painters favored forming societies for social and commercial purposes. Many of the significant art societies of the time were located in and around Yuyuan Garden. For example, in the first year of the Tongzhi era (1862), Wu Jialin founded the “Pinghua Calligraphy and Painting Society” in Yuyuan Garden. This was followed by the “Feidan Pavilion Calligraphy and Painting Society”, the “Hai Shang Ti Jin Guan Calligraphy and Painting Society”, and the “Wanmi Mountain House Calligraphy and Painting Society”, all of which were established in Yuyuan Garden. The most influential society was the “Yuyuan Calligraphy and Painting Charity Society”, founded in the first year of the Xuantong era (1909), with its headquarters at the Deyue Building in Yuyuan Garden. The first president was Qian Huian, succeeded later by Wu Changshuo, Wang Yiting, and others. Members included prominent Shanghai calligraphers and painters such as Gao Yong, Yang Yi, Cheng Zhang, Huang Shanshou, Pu Hua, Shen Xinhai, Wang Zhongshan, and Cheng Yaoshen, essentially encompassing the major figures in Shanghai’s art scene at the time. The society established regulations for regular meetings, artwork appraisal, and art exchange, and held annual exhibitions. They also collected membership fees, set standards for artistic commissions, and divided the proceeds between the artist and the society. The society used half the funds for charitable activities, including disaster relief, and continued this practice annually. In the summer, they distributed medicine; in the winter, they gave out rice. They also provided relief to victims of floods and droughts. This practice continued year

after year, becoming a regular tradition. The “Yuyuan Calligraphy and Painting Charity Society” was known for its charitable nature, emphasizing the responsibility of “helping the needy and supporting the distressed”.¹⁶ For example, the Ti Jin Guan, established in 1875 at Zhabei, Shanghai (now Zhaotong Road), was not only a residence for artists like Wu Changshuo, Wang Yiting, Huang Binhong, and Wang Geqi but also served as a sales venue. “Calligraphy and painting brokers often brought many calligraphy, painting, and antique items to Ti Jin Guan for sale, and Ti Jin Guan handled the sales of calligraphy and painting works for its members. Artisans from other regions who came to Shanghai to sell seals, calligraphy, and paintings would also use Ti Jin Guan for their commissions and to find sales channels for their works.”¹⁷ Shanghai’s calligraphers and painters also had a strong sense of social responsibility. They frequently joined forces to provide disaster relief, assist people experiencing poverty, and aid refugees, turning their art resources into social resources for disaster relief. This charitable work not only accumulated benevolence but also expanded the social influence of the Shanghai School. For instance, the Shanghai newspaper *Shun Pao*, which had the largest circulation at the time, published dozens of advertisements in 1878 about the charitable contributions of calligraphers and painters.¹⁸ Within the Shanghai School artist community, there was a trend of encouraging and supporting young talents. For example, the case of Zhu Fukan illustrates this well. According to Feng Guangjian, when Zhu Fukan met Wu Changshuo at the age of seven, Wu was impressed by Zhu’s mastery of the *Stone Drum Inscriptions* and referred to him as “Little Friend”. Kang Youwei also praised him as a “child prodigy”. Zhang Meiyi, the principal of the South Sea Public School (predecessor to Shanghai Jiaotong University), admired the “child prodigy” and took him under his wing. At seventeen, Zhu Fukan joined the Ti Jin Guan Calligraphy and Painting Society, becoming the youngest member. The society’s leaders included Wu Changshuo, Wang Yiting, Yu Yushuang, and Ren Jinshu, with members such as Xu Zhuxian, Cheng Yaoshen, Shang Shengbo, Yao Yuqin, Xiong Songquan, Zeng Nongran, Li Meian, Qian Shoutie, He Tianjian, Zheng Xiaoxu, and Zhang Daqian. After the reorganization, members included Tan Yankai and Yu Youren, providing Zhu with many opportunities to interact with and learn from famous artists. His works were compiled in the *National Famous Seal Selection*, and the Shanghai Youzheng Press published *Zhu Baihang’s Han, Li, and Wei Calligraphy Copybook*. At twenty-seven, the *Jingkan Seal Collection*, recommended and reviewed by Wu Changshuo, was

published by the Commercial Press, gaining domestic and international fame. Zhu was later invited by Liu Haisu to teach at the Shanghai Fine Arts Academy and served as a member of the Chinese Painting Association committee.¹⁹ This demonstrates that nurturing and supporting promising young artists was also prevalent.

The fourth essential factor in the formation of the Shanghai School of Calligraphy was the powerful influence of publishing and media at the time. This publishing power greatly promoted the development of Shanghai School calligraphy and painting. The Commercial Press was among the earliest in China to use the collotype printing technology and published many calligraphy and seal carving works, totaling over a hundred titles. In the 25th year of the Republic of China (1936), the press published *Collection of Books and Records, First Compilation*, edited by Wang Yunwu. This collection included numerous works related to calligraphy, painting, and inscriptions, such as *Wu County Inscriptions*, *Central Plain Inscriptions*, *Selected Tang Stele from Su Zhai*, *Xian Zhe Xuan Examination on Model Books*, *Iron Box Studio Inscriptions on Gold and Stone*, and *Qian Mountain Hall Calligraphy and Painting Records*, all in convenient single volumes. The Shenzhou Guoguang Society, founded by Huang Binhong and Deng Shi in 1901, also played a significant role. This society published numerous books on calligraphy, painting, and seal carving. Their notable publications included the *Shenzhou Guoguang Collection* and *Shenzhou Grand View*, edited by Huang Binhong, which featured many famous ancient and contemporary paintings and calligraphy. In 1911, they published the *Fine Arts Series*, consisting of thirty volumes and one hundred and twenty books covering various aspects of calligraphy and painting, including theory, appreciation, examination, history, cataloging, and techniques. Besides these series, the society released many individual volumes on inscriptions and seal carving. In 1906, Yu Fu and Lian Nanhua established the Wenming Bookstore in Shanghai. The bookstore’s calligraphy books were categorized into three types: fine collotype editions, ordinary stone-printed editions, and student editions, referred to as *practice tie* or *large character practice tie*. Each category catered to its specific audience, demonstrating the leadership’s insight and strategy. The Youzheng Bookstore, founded by Di Pingzi in Shanghai in 1904, specialized in reproducing and distributing stele and painting albums. The bookstore was renowned for its large-scale publication of stele and painting books, producing over 800 titles from its founding until its closure in 1943, with a significant portion being collotype editions. Their categorization

included colotype stele books, a stele from the Southern and Northern Dynasties, famous calligraphy of various dynasties, famous people's handwritten documents, poetry manuscripts, character screens, and large couplets. In 1918 alone, the bookstore published eighty-six titles of *celebrity calligraphy* and over thirty colotype stele books, with works like *Nantang Chengqing Hall Tie* and *Dunhuang Stone Room Secrets* becoming prized collectibles today. Yuzheng Bookstore held a prominent place in the publication of calligraphy rubbings, excelling in variety and quality. Apart from calligraphy rubbings, another significant contribution of Yuzheng Bookstore was the extensive publication of original rubbing for seal collections. Collectors highly seek these collections at today's rare book auctions. Other significant publishers included Shanggu Mountain Studio, Zhonghua Book Company, and Yiyuan Zhenshang Society, which published numerous works on inscriptions, calligraphy, and painting, including high-quality colotype editions.²⁰ Many calligraphers from other regions who settled in Shanghai initially took up media-related jobs, such as editing newspapers and periodicals. Notable figures included Huang Binhong, Zhang Yuanji, Tang Tuo, Chen Dingshan, Wang Dungen, Zheng Wuchang, Wang Yachen, Huang Baoyue, Li Shutong, Ma Xulun, and Bai Jiao.

Another crucial reason for the existence and development of a school of painting and calligraphy is the emphasis on education, which can be considered the fifth factor in the continuity of the Shanghai School art. During the Republic of China period, calligraphy education included traditional master-apprentice methods, such as family education, private school education, apprenticeships with calligraphers, and Western-style school education. Generally, calligraphy often started with family and private school education. Let's take Sha Menghai and Wang Quchang as examples: "He (Sha Menghai) liked observing his father write, paint, and carve seals while sitting beside his father's desk...Besides his daily private school lessons, his father taught him a few seal script characters daily."²¹ "In 1903, Wang Quchang's uncle introduced him to elementary books like *Wenzi Cangqiu* and taught him to trace characters with a brush. Children from bureaucratic or scholarly families often had superior conditions for learning calligraphy. Families with a tradition of scholarship usually had a high cultural level, and the highest calligraphy practitioners in the family often served as instructors, which was very beneficial for the student's development in calligraphy."²² Apprenticeships were an important part of the inheritance and development of calligraphy. Zheng Yimei once described and recorded the scene of Wu Changshuo's disciples: "All those who sold their art

were known to have come from Wu Changshuo's school, totaling about a hundred or more. However, according to those familiar with Changshuo, although the number of disciples was large, it was not as grand as outsiders claimed. Notable among them were Chen Qingshan from Zhejiang, whose floral painting closely resembled his master's, and Wu Xing's Zhu Wenyun, who spent over ten years with Changshuo, creating bamboo and stone paintings with a refined charm. Another was Yun Jian's Kuai Zigou, who excelled in floral paintings. Chen Jianan from Hangzhou mastered both calligraphy and painting. Wu Qizhi from Wuxing was also skilled. Wu Songling and Wang Kedu, who not only practiced seal carving but also created floral paintings that were highly realistic. Among them, Zhao Ziyun from Wu, who adopted the pen name Yunhe and was known as He Dao Ren, was the most talented, inheriting Changshuo's teachings in seal script and floral painting. Changshuo, feeling weary in his later years, would often delegate requests to Ziyun, who faithfully carried out his master's wishes. Ziyun also practiced cursive and clerical scripts and landscapes, embodying the spirit of Zheng Gukou and Shitao. Changshuo, upon seeing Ziyun's work, felt inferior. Ziyun, who had lived in Shanghai's Xinzhai Road for a long time, later moved his family to Suzhou, planting flowers and trees in his new home. He repeatedly invited me to visit and discussed good ideas, but I could not fulfill this wish due to my mundane life. Another prominent figure was Xu Huisheng, who held his post for several months before Changshuo passed away from a stroke, leaving his work unfinished. Other notable figures who preceded Changshuo included Chen Shizeng, Xu Xingzhou, Liu Yulan, and Zhao Shinong. Shizeng's paintings and Shinong's seals were well-known across Jiangnan and beyond. Xingzhou's inscriptions traced back to the Qin and Han dynasties, left the *Lotus Flower Hall Seals Book* in circulation, and Yulan was skilled in finger painting, with techniques as refined as a sharp pen. Changshuo's disciples were formidable, comparable to Zheng Nongran and Li Meian's."²³

During the Republican era, calligraphy education was thriving with six major schools of thought, each represented by prominent figures: Li Ruiqing's "Li School", Kang Youwei's "Kang School", Wu Changshuo's "Wu School", Zheng Xiaoxu's "Zheng School", Yu Youren's "Yu School", and Zeng Xi's "Zeng School". For instance, Li Ruiqing's followers included figures like Li Jian, Hu Xiaoshi, Zhang Daqian, Ling Yunchao, Wei Letang, Zhang Longyan, Li Xiren, and Li Zhenxing. They were well-trained in Li's aesthetic ideals of integrating seal script with regular script. These disciples, particularly Li Jian, Hu Xiaoshi, and Zhang Daqian,

are considered the top students of Li Ruiqing.²⁴ Importantly, many of these disciples trained in the traditional master-apprentice system later became key figures in the newly established Western-style educational institutions, laying a solid foundation for the development of the Shanghai School. For example:

Li School: Elite Hu Xiaoshi went on to teach at several institutions, including Beijing Women's Higher Normal School, Fourth Zhongshan University, National Central University in Nanjing, and Jinling University. Lü Fengzi graduated from Liangjiang Superior Normal School, taught at Fourth Zhongshan University, Jinling University, and National Art College, and founded the Zhengze Women's Vocational School. Li Jian taught at Liangjiang Superior Normal School.

Kang School: Elite Xu Beihong taught at National Central University's Department of Fine Arts, Peking University's Art School, and Peking Art College and was the president of Central Academy of Fine Arts. Liu Haisu and Wu Shiguang and Zhang Zhaoguang founded Shanghai Fine Arts School in 1912 and served as its principal.

Wu School: Elite Zhu Lesan was appointed at Shanghai Fine Arts School, Shanghai New Art College, Shanghai Changming Art College, Shanghai Chinese Art University, and National Art College. He also established and taught China's first calligraphy engraving department in 1963 alongside Pan Tianshou, Lu Weizhao, and Sha Menghai.

In summary, the formation of Haipai calligraphy and

painting art is the result of the convergence of various factors, including historical context, economic conditions, social atmosphere, collective efforts, and the innovative spirit of the artists. Haipai art's ability to incorporate characteristics from different schools, embrace diverse artistic styles, and continuously explore and innovate allows it to maintain its vitality and relevance to this day.

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海派書法的形成

胡傳海

摘要: 上海具有了一個藝術流派所必須擁有的條件, 優越的地理環境, 寬鬆的政治氛圍, 極強的經濟動能, 出色的藝術領袖, 龐大的收藏人群, 成群的藝術團體, 強大的出版傳媒, 良好的教育傳承等等, 這一切催發了海派書法的誕生, 同時也成為中國現當代藝術史上最具有生命力的藝術流派並影響至今。

關鍵詞: 文化多元; 利益驅動; 中堅力量; 心理認同